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Scanning the Issue

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Scanning the Issue

The current issue of The European Journal of Research and Development (Vol 2, Issue 4, December 2022) contains 28 articles.

Physicochemical and sensory parameters of vegan water kefir beverages fermented with different fruits

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.119>

Classification Mental Workload Levels from EEG Signals with 1D Convolutional Neural Network

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.193>

Development of Dimensional Measurement Methods with a 3D Measuring Device without Using a Checking Fixture

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.125>

The Certification Steps for the Additively Manufactured Aviation-Grade Parts: Certification Steps

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.133>

Coating Machine Developed For Technical And Smart Textile Applications

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.137>

Development of Hardness Test Device for Determination of Comfort Parameters in Pillows and Experimental Study of Hardness Measurement

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.143>

Method and Device for Determining Comfort in Seating Groups and Comparison of Subjective and Objective Evaluations

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.144>

Block Sponge Compression and Packaging System Design and Analysis with Finite Element Method

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.122>

Optimization of Thermal Comfort Properties in Duvets by Thermal Resistance Measurements in Home Textile Products

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.146>

Design of Wavelength Selectively Metamaterial Antenna for Thermal Camouflage

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.181>

Investigation of One Bath Dyeing Processes of PES/CO Mixed Towel Products and Investigation of Test Results

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.139>

The Investigation Of Basic Yellow 28 Adsorption by Using Different Carbon Material

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.168>

Development of Air Driver Seat for Use in M3/N3 Class Vehicles

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.171>

Multi-Chemistry Battery Management System for Electric Vehicles

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.176>

Investigation on the Fastness and Dimensional Stability of the Knitted Fabrics Made of the New Generation Regenerated Cellulose Fibers

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.179>

Remote Management and Tracking System for Commercial Refrigerators Using UHF RFID Technology

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.172>

Development of Deflector Structure and Effects on Performance: Refrigerated Display Cabinet Application

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.190>

Microstrip Reflectarray Design for 26 GHz

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.191>

Design Automation of a Two Scissors Lift

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.192>

Effect on Strength of Different Fiber Orientation Angles of the Composite Plate Under Out of Plane Load

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.167>

Increasing Efficiency by Applying a New Generation Dual-Core Transformer Design

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.121>

Water - Based Polyurethanes for Antibacterial Coatings: an Overview

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.124>

Platform Independent Embedded Linux OTA Method

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.165>

Opportunities to Production of Biofuel from Grains and to Improve the Factors Increasing the Yield of Bioethanol in a Short Time

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.145>

Benchmarking Health Infrastructure in Türkiye and Other OECD Countries: Health Workforce, Medical Technology and R&D Activities in Health

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.145>

Improving the Properties of Biodegradable PLA via Blending with Polyesters for Industrial Applications

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.201>

Improvement of the Comfort Features of Denim Products

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.202>

Design and Prototype Production of Scissor Lift Platform 25 Tons Capacity

<https://doi.org/10.56038/ejrnd.v2i4.177>